

Estimation of Mixed (Burr type XII and Exponential) Distribution Parameters

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Abstract:

Many mixed distributions with various number of parameters can be generated from current distributions using the blending parameters s_w ; where $0 \leq s_\pi \leq 1$ and $\sum_{w=1}^K s_\pi = 1$. This research goals to utilize the concept of combining two distributions (Burr type XII and Exponential) with unbalanced scale coefficients to obtain a mixed distribution. These generated distributions were combined using the blending parameter w_k which determines the percentage of contribution rate of each distribution to the resulting distribution.

The significance of this study lies in developing a more adaptable distribution that can be used in statistical applications. Two estimation methods, namely maximum likelihood estimation (MLE) and ordinary least squares (OLS), were used to estimate the parameters of the generating mixed distribution. Simulation studies were also conducted to verify the properties of the generating mixed distribution and utilize the two estimating methods to estimate its parameters.

Keywords: *blending parameters, mixed distribution, statistical applications, simulation studies.*

Introduction

Probability distributions are an essential tool in data analysis and interpretation of various phenomena in many fields, such as statistics, economics, and natural sciences. However, the complexity of the attitude of real data, which is depicted by high degrees of skewness and flatness, calls for the development of new probability models that are more flexible. In recent years, researchers have begun to explore the possibility of creating mixed distributions by merging traditional continuous and discontinuous distributions. These studies aim to produce new distributions with flexible properties that are able to describe the behavior of data more accurately.

This research addresses a recent idea of how to find a generated mixed distribution by combining two distributions, where each distribution includes a number of parameters. It is expected that this will lead to the production of a new distribution containing a larger number of parameters, which increases the flexibility of statistical applications.

The research will focus on developing the basic functions of the mixed distribution (MD), for instance the probability density function (P.D.F), the cumulative distribution function (C.D.F), the reliability function (R.F), the hazard rate function (H.F), and some properties of the distribution using the mixture parameter that illustrates the percentage of contribution rate of each of the joint distributions in forming the mixture distribution. multiple studies about

mixed distributions introduced advancement in this field. In Kazmi and Aslam (2019) proposed a study of the generalized exponential distribution with three components on first-type control data. The maximum likelihood method (M.L.E) and Bayes method (B.M) were used using loss functions (L.F) (square error, precautionary loss, and the DeGroot loss function) to estimator the parameters of the mixed distribution (M.D) using Monte Carlo Simulation method and with different sample sizes. The researchers came to the conclusion that the Bayes method is better under the DeGroot loss function than the maximum likelihood method (M.L.E) for the inverse Rayleigh. The researchers also discussed the different distribution properties such as risk, reliability and moments. In Sah and A. Mishra (2019) published a study of a mixed distribution (Generalized Exponential- Lindley Mixture of Poisson Distribution (GELMPD) with three components. The researchers discussed some of the properties, and the distribution parameters were estimated using the methods of moments and maximum likelihood. The researchers concluded that this distribution is more suitable for most discrete data sets with negative binomials. In Teamah, et al. (2020) published a study of a mixed distribution (Frchet, Weibull and Exponential) with three components, and the researchers discussed some of the properties, and the distribution parameters were estimated using the maximum likelihood method (M.L.E), and the researchers concluded when applying this distribution to real data that this distribution is more adaptable and comprehensive than the single distributions. In Hussain, & Shareef, (2021) published a study of a mixed distribution (Weibull, Raleigh and Exponential (WRE)) with three components. The researchers discussed some of the properties, and the distribution parameters were estimated using the maximum likelihood method and the moment method. When the researchers applied this distribution to real data, they concluded that this distribution is more adaptable and comprehensive than the single distributions.

Methodology

Let x be r.v from Burr type XII distribution (B.D) with shape parameter (S.P) (p) and scale parameter (S.P) (b); then the (p.d.f) is define as (Usta, 2013; Tahir, et al., 2018):

$$f(x, b, p) = pb x^{b-1} [1 + x^b]^{-(p+1)} \quad (1)$$

$$x > 0 \quad p, b > 0$$

And another r.v $z=x$ from Exponential distribution (E.D) with (S.P) (θ); then the (p.d.f) is define as (Mohammed, & Ugwuowo, 2020; Shareef, & Hussain, 2023):

$$f(x, \theta) = \theta e^{-\theta x} \quad (2)$$

$$x > 0 \quad \theta > 0$$

Consequently, the probability density function (p.d.f) of mixture distribution (M.D) can be get from mixing the (p.d.f) in equation's (1) and (2) by applying the subsequent rule (Osatohanmwun, Oyegue, & Ogbonmwan, 2019; Shareef, & Hussain, 2023):

$$\therefore f_{Be}(x, p, b, \theta) = \pi f_B(x) + (1 - \pi) f_E(x)$$

Where π represents weight of each distribution
Such that

$$\int_0^{\infty} f(x) dx = 1 \quad \text{and } f(x) > 0$$

$$\int_0^{\infty} \pi (pb x^{b-1} [1 + x^b]^{-(p+1)}) + (1 - \pi) \theta e^{-\theta x} dx \quad (3)$$

After solving equation (3), we get the probability density function (p.d.f) of mixing distribution with four parameter.

$$f_{Be}(x, p, b, \theta) = \pi (pb x^{b-1} [1 + x^b]^{-(p+1)}) + (1 - \pi) \theta e^{-\theta x}$$

$$x > 0 \quad p, b, \theta > 0 \quad (4)$$

Figure 1. Show the P.D.F of the Mixed (Burr type XII and Exponential) Distribution

$$f_{Be}(x, p, b, \theta) = p_r(X \leq x)$$

$$f_{Be}(x, p, b, \theta) = \int_0^x f(u) du$$

$$F(x, p, b, \theta) = \pi(1 - [1 + x^b]^{-p}) + (1 - \pi)(1 - e^{-\theta x}) \quad (5)$$

Figure 2. Show the C.F of the Mixed (Burr type XII and Exponential) Distribution

The characteristics of mixed distribution (M.D) can be derived from *pdf*.

Moment Function

Is define as

$$\mu_r' = E(x^r)$$

$$\mu_r' = \int_0^{\infty} x^r f(x) dx$$

$$\mu_r' = \int_0^{\infty} x^r [\pi(p b x^{b-1} [1 + x^b]^{-(p+1)}) + (1 - \pi)\theta e^{-\theta x}] dx$$

$$\mu_r' = \pi \frac{\Gamma(k - \frac{r}{c}) \Gamma(\frac{r}{c} + 1)}{k} + (1 - \pi) \theta^{\frac{1}{r}} \Gamma(r + 1) \quad (6)$$

Where $r = 1$ we get the mean of mixture distribution

$$\mu_1' = \pi \frac{\Gamma(k - \frac{1}{c}) \Gamma(\frac{1}{c} + 1)}{k} + (1 - \pi)\theta$$

Where $r = 2$ we get the mean of mixture distribution

$$\mu_2' = \pi \frac{\Gamma(k - \frac{2}{c}) \Gamma(\frac{2}{c} + 1)}{k} + 2(1 - \pi)\theta$$

Where $r = 3$ we get the mean of mixture distribution

$$\mu_3' = \pi \frac{\Gamma(k - \frac{3}{c}) \Gamma(\frac{3}{c} + 1)}{k} + 6(1 - \pi)\theta$$

Where $r = 4$ we get the mean of mixture distribution

$$\mu_4' = \pi \frac{\Gamma(k - \frac{4}{c}) \Gamma(\frac{4}{c} + 1)}{k} + 24(1 - \pi)\theta$$

Variance

Is define as:

$$var(x) = E(x^2) - (E(x))^2$$

$$var(x) = \pi \frac{\Gamma(k - \frac{2}{c}) \Gamma(\frac{2}{c} + 1)}{k} + 2(1 - \pi)\theta - (\pi \frac{\Gamma(k - \frac{1}{c}) \Gamma(\frac{1}{c} + 1)}{k} + (1 - \pi)\theta)^2 \quad (7)$$

Reliability Function

The Reliability function is define as (Fify, & Mead, 2017):

$$R(t) = 1 - F(x)$$

$$R(t) = 1 - \left[\pi(1 - [1 + x^b]^{-p}) + (1 - \pi)(1 - e^{-\theta x}) \right] \quad (8)$$

Figure 3. Show the Reliability Function of the Mixed Distribution

Hazard Function

Hazard Function is define as:

$$h(x) = \frac{f(x)}{R(x)}$$

$$h(x) = \frac{\pi(p b x^{b-1} [1+x^b]^{-(p+1)} + (1-\pi)\theta e^{-\theta x})}{1 - [\pi(1 - [1+x^b]^{-p}) + (1-\pi)(1 - e^{-\theta x})]} \quad (9)$$

Figure 4. Show the Hazard Function of the Mixed Distribution

Measure of Skewness and Kurtosis

Is define as:

$$S = \frac{(m_3)^2}{(m_2)^3}$$

$$S = \frac{(\pi \frac{\Gamma(k-\frac{3}{c})\Gamma(\frac{3}{c}+1)}{k} + 6(1-\pi)\theta)^2}{(\pi \frac{\Gamma(k-\frac{2}{c})\Gamma(\frac{2}{c}+1)}{k} + 2(1-\pi)\theta)^3} \quad (10)$$

And

$$K = \frac{m_4}{(m_2)^2}$$

$$K = \frac{\pi \frac{\Gamma(k-\frac{4}{c})\Gamma(\frac{4}{c}+1)}{k} + 24(1-\pi)\theta}{(\pi \frac{\Gamma(k-\frac{2}{c})\Gamma(\frac{2}{c}+1)}{k} + 2(1-\pi)\theta)^2} \quad (11)$$

Moment Generating Function

Moment Generating Function is define as:

$$M_x(t) = E(e^{xt})$$

$$\text{Where } E(e^{xt}) = \int_0^{\infty} e^{xt} f(x) dx$$

$$E(e^{xt}) = \int_0^{\infty} e^{xt} \left[p \left(c k s^{-c} x^{c-1} \left[1 + \left(\frac{x}{s} \right)^c \right]^{-k-1} \right) + q \theta e^{-\theta x} \right] dx$$

$$E(e^{xt}) = \pi \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{(t)^j \Gamma(k-\frac{j}{c})\Gamma(\frac{j}{c}+1)}{j! \Gamma k} + (1 - \pi) \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (t\theta)^j \Gamma(j+1) \quad (12)$$

Characteristic Function

Characteristic Function is define as:

$$\phi_x(t) = E(e^{ixt})$$

$$E(e^{ixt}) = \pi \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{(it)^j \Gamma(k-\frac{j}{c})\Gamma(\frac{j}{c}+1)}{j! \Gamma k} + (1 - \pi) \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (it\theta)^j \Gamma(j+1) \quad (13)$$

Estimation Method

The parameter of the M.D (π, p, b, θ) will be estimated using the two estimation techniques that are provided in this section. These techniques, which are converted in the next subsection, are maximum likelihood (MEL) and ordinary least square (OLS).

Maximum Likelihood Estimation (M.L.E)

the M.L.E function can be represented as

$$L(x) = \prod_{i=1}^n [\pi(p b x^{b-1} [1+x^b]^{-(p+1)}) + (1-\pi)\theta e^{-\theta x}]$$

$$\ln(L(x)) = \sum_{i=1}^n \ln[\pi(p b x^{b-1} [1+x^b]^{-(p+1)}) + (1-\pi)\theta e^{-\theta x}]$$

$$\frac{\partial \ln(L)}{\partial p} = \frac{\pi(1+x^b)^{-p-1} \ln(1+x^b)}{\sum_{i=1}^n [\pi(p b x^{b-1} [1+x^b]^{-(p+1)}) + (1-\pi)\theta e^{-\theta x}]} \quad (14)$$

$$\frac{\partial \ln(L)}{\partial \pi} = \frac{p b x^{b-1} (1+x^b)^{-p-1} - \theta e^{-\theta x}}{\sum_{i=1}^n [\pi(p b x^{b-1} [1+x^b]^{-(p+1)}) + (1-\pi)\theta e^{-\theta x}]} \quad (15)$$

$$\frac{\partial \ln(L)}{\partial b} = \frac{\pi p x^{b-1} (1+x^b)^{-p-1} - \ln(1+x^b)}{\sum_{i=1}^n [\pi(p b x^{b-1} [1+x^b]^{-(p+1)}) + (1-\pi)\theta e^{-\theta x}]} \quad (16)$$

$$\frac{\partial \ln(L)}{\partial \theta} = \frac{-(1-\pi)x e^{-\theta x}}{\sum_{i=1}^n [\pi(p b x^{b-1} [1+x^b]^{-(p+1)}) + (1-\pi)\theta e^{-\theta x}]} \quad (17)$$

Where we notice that equations (14), (15), (16) and (17) are non-linear equations (N.L.E), so it is difficult to find them, one of the numerical techniques will be employed such as **Newton-Raphson** method to find the estimated parameters.

Ordinary Least Square Method (OLS)

This method depends on Minimizing the sum of squares(M.S.S) of random errors and can be define as:

$$OLS = \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\left(\frac{i}{n+1} \right) - F(x) \right]^2$$

Note that $\left(\frac{i}{n+1} \right)$ is the amount of non-parametric

$$OLS = \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\left(\frac{i}{n+1} \right) - [\pi(1 - [1+x^b]^{-p}) + (1-\pi)(1 - e^{-\theta x})] \right]^2$$

$$\frac{\partial OLS}{\partial \pi} = 2 \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\left(\frac{i}{n+1} \right) - [\pi(1 - [1+x^b]^{-p}) + (1-\pi)(1 - e^{-\theta x})] \right] * (1+x^b)^{-p} - \theta e^{-\theta x} \quad (18)$$

$$\frac{\partial OLS}{\partial p} = 2 \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\left(\frac{i}{n+1} \right) - [\pi(1 - [1+x^b]^{-p}) + (1-\pi)(1 - e^{-\theta x})] \right] * \pi(1+x^b)^{-p} - \ln(1+x^b) \quad (19)$$

$$\frac{\partial OLS}{\partial b} = -2 \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\left(\frac{i}{n+1} \right) - [\pi(1 - [1+x^b]^{-p}) + (1-\pi)(1 - e^{-\theta x})] \right] * \pi p x^{b-1} (1+x^b)^{-p} \ln(1+x^b) \quad (20)$$

$$\frac{\partial OLS}{\partial \theta} = -2 \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\left(\frac{i}{n+1} \right) - [\pi(1 - [1+x^b]^{-p}) + (1-\pi)(1 - e^{-\theta x})] \right] * (1-\pi)x e^{-\theta x} \quad (21)$$

We observe that the equations (18),(19), (20) and (21) are N.L.E, so it is difficult to find them, one of the numerical techniques will be employed such as **Newton-Raphson** method to find the estimated parameters.

Simulation Studies

In the previous section, two methods for estimating mixed distributions using M.L.E and O.L.S, and they were estimated on a Discrimination equations were also chosen for both methods. In practical terms, the method of distribution, rejection and distribution data was used, due to the difficulty of obtaining the cumulative distribution function(C.D.F) using the inverse transformation method. To compensate the simulator to estimate data parameters through adjustment methods and simulation program for Matlab14.

The default parameters listed below were utilized to estimate the mixture distribution parameters:

Table 1. The Initial Values of Mixed Distribution Parameters(M.D) According to the Estimation Methods

model	π	p	b	θ
1	0.5	1	1.5	0.5
2	0.7	3	2	1
3	0.4	2	2	1

Four different samples (25,75,100 and 150). Were employed for the evaluation and contrasted the estimate techniques using. The sum of squares of error (MSE) scale, which can be calculation using the formula below:

$$MSE_{(\hat{p})} = \frac{\sum_1^s (\hat{p}-p)^2}{s}$$

On Matlab 2014 program using simulation program was used to estimate the parameters and the results represent in the following tables were reached:

Discussion of the Results

Table 2. The Estimated Values of Distribution Parameters Based on the Estimation Method, Along with the Best Method According to Criterion MSE when $\pi = 0.5, p = 1, b = 1.5, \theta = 0.5$

n	method	π	p	b	θ
		0.5	1	1.5	0.5
25	Est.mle	0.0546	0.1641	0.0841	0.0743
	mse.mle	0.0027	0.0016	0.0022	0.0025
	Est.ols	0.0488	0.1594	0.0788	0.0702
	mse.ols	0.0004	0.0008	0.0008	0.0011
75	Est.mle	0.0537	0.1628	0.0837	0.0742
	mse.mle	0.0023	0.0014	0.0023	0.0021
	Est.ols	0.0486	0.1582	0.0781	0.0683
	mse.ols	0.0008	0.0007	0.0007	0.0007
100	Est.mle	0.0525	0.1627	0.0822	0.0725
	mse.mle	0.0013	0.0016	0.0015	0.0016
	Est.ols	0.0477	0.1575	0.0775	0.0673
	mse.ols	0.0006	0.0006	0.0007	0.0006
150	Est.mle	0.0514	0.1618	0.0815	0.0713
	mse.mle	0.0011	0.0012	0.0013	0.0014
	Est.ols	0.0467	0.1564	0.0762	0.0667
	mse.ols	0.0004	0.0004	0.0004	0.0005

Table 3. The Estimated Values of Distribution Parameters Based on the Estimation Method, Along with the Best Method According to Criterion MSE when $\pi = 0.7, p = 3, b = 2, \theta = 1$

n	method	π	P	b	θ
		0.7	3	2	1
25	Est.mle	0.1642	0.0839	0.0751	0.1939
	mse.mle	0.0017	0.0011	0.0022	0.0015
	Est.ols	0.1591	0.0797	0.0695	0.1898
	mse.ols	0.0009	0.0009	0.0008	0.0009
75	Est.mle	0.1635	0.0836	0.0736	0.1932
	mse.mle	0.0016	0.0023	0.0014	0.0017
	Est.ols	0.1588	0.0785	0.0686	0.1884
	mse.ols	0.0010	0.0009	0.0008	0.0005
100	Est.mle	0.1628	0.0822	0.0727	0.1924
	mse.mle	0.0014	0.0014	0.0014	0.0015
	Est.ols	0.1576	0.0773	0.0672	0.1877
	mse.ols	0.0006	0.0004	0.0005	0.0006
150	Est.mle	0.1614	0.0811	0.0713	0.1911
	mse.mle	0.0010	0.0013	0.0012	0.0015
	Est.ols	0.1567	0.0765	0.0668	0.1865
	mse.ols	0.0005	0.0004	0.0004	0.0004

Table 4. The Estimated Values of Distribution Parameters Based on the Estimation Method, Along with the Best Method According to Criterion MSE Standard when $\pi = 0.4, p = 2, b = 2, \theta = 1$

n	method	π	P	b	θ
		0.4	2	2	1
25	Est.mle	0.1087	0.1688	0.1494	0.3896
	mse.mle	0.0049	0.0042	0.0041	0.0040
	Est.ols	0.0991	0.1588	0.1392	0.3793
	mse.ols	0.0021	0.0015	0.0019	0.0025
75	Est.mle	0.1075	0.1676	0.1467	0.3860
	mse.mle	0.0054	0.0031	0.0037	0.0028
	Est.ols	0.0966	0.1571	0.1373	0.3773
	mse.ols	0.0015	0.0014	0.0019	0.0018
100	Est.mle	0.1049	0.1656	0.1442	0.3859
	mse.mle	0.0030	0.0033	0.0033	0.0034
	Est.ols	0.0949	0.1548	0.1350	0.3749
	mse.ols	0.0010	0.0011	0.0011	0.0013
150	Est.mle	0.1034	0.1633	0.1428	0.3826
	mse.mle	0.0031	0.0023	0.0027	0.0028
	Est.ols	0.0934	0.1531	0.1329	0.3728
	mse.ols	0.0009	0.0008	0.0007	0.0009

The results are shown in Tables 2,3,4. The best parameter estimate was at a sample size of 150, yielding the lowest mean sum of square errors (MSE) from the sample sizes tested. With estimated values of parameters. The sample size of 150 is the most accurate estimate. These results indicate that the (OLS) method was more effective in estimating the mixed distribution parameters (M.D) than the maximum likelihood method based on the mean square error.

Conclusions

1. The researcher worked on the use of the mixing parameter by inserting it into the single distributions, namely the Burr type XII and Exponential distribution, resulting in the mixed distribution (Burr type XII and Exponential) and then proving that the distribution is a probability.
2. The comparison results between the Ordinary Least Squares method(L.O.S) and the Maximum Likelihood method(M.L.E) showed that the best method was O.L.S for sample size 150 according to the average sum of the squares of error.

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